

An Investigation in to the Causes and Effects of Sport Violence in Selected Secondary Schools in Bo City, Southern Province, Sierra Leone

Sandy Mohamed Koroma

Lecturer, Eastern Polytechnic, Kenema, Eastern Region, Republic of Sierra Leone

Abstract— This work investigated the causes and effects of sport violence among selected secondary schools in Bo city, Southern Province, Sierra Leone. It examined the various variables that are required to reduce the occurrence of violent behavior in senior secondary school sports. The work further sounded the independent opinion of student athletes, teachers, supporters, administrators, and stakeholders on how effectively this social problem can be managed and minimized.

The relevant data required for the study were collected from the population comprising principals of senior secondary schools, teachers of physical

Health education department, teachers of the games committee, parents and guardians of students from the selected secondary schools.

The methodology employed was a descriptive case of study using well designed questionnaires, personal observation and interviews.

The data collected were analyzed through the use of semi-statistical computations and percentages.

The investigation revealed that the lack of knowledge of the rules of engagement by teachers, administrators, athletes of the schools, supporters within the schools has culminated to violent behavior.

The inadequate means of information dissemination of group rules, the lack of appropriate facilities are all contributing factors to this problem. The absence of punishment code for defaulters and violators of the rules and laws of competition in addition to the use of performance enhancing drugs by athletes, coaches and team supporters are contributing factors to the problem of sport violence. Subsequently, Sport officials, students athletes, officials, teachers are victimized while equipment and facilities are vandalized. Most often, this awkward scenario results into the use of abusive languages on supporters, athletes and school teachers most common.

The use of dangerous missiles with intent of destroying human life and property especially expensive equipment are common results of riotous conduct when most competitions are held.

The involvement of stakeholders such as teachers, referees, coaches, administrators and parents who are sport lovers, the effective methods of information sharing and networking by all those concerned. The efficient enforcement of rules by sport administrators were recommended as suitable solutions to minimize violence in senior secondary school sport.

I. INTRODUCTION/BACKGROUND

Many schools of thought in the field of sociology and psychology have tried to define the term violence or aggression in various ways. For some, aggression is the use of excessive physical force; which has the potential to cause harm or destruction. Others refer to aggression as a verbal or physical behavior grounded with intent to dominate, control or

do harm to another person. Aggression is often involved in violence.

Psychologists have further defined violence as a form of behavior directed towards the goal of harming or injuring another living person, who is motivated to avoid such a treatment (Baion 1999). The term violence seems to draw association with aggression and thus produce positive or negative value judgments and emotional responses (Gill, 1986)

Violence is often regarded as actions that are illegal or unsanctioned, but the situation in which the use of violence is encouraged or approved in a group or a community is uncalled for. When violence occurs in connection with deviant unconformity or a rejection or norms in society, it is classified as illegal and is sanctioned vehemently.

The Instinct Theory according to (Gill 1986) maintains that people have an instinct to be aggressive that builds up until it must be inevitably expressed. The instinct can be either expressed directly by attacking another living Being or displayed through catharsis where aggression is released or "blown off" through socially desirable means of sport. For an instinct theory, sport and exercise play a vital role in society in that they allow people to channel their aggressive instincts in socially acceptable ways. Unfortunately no biological inborn aggressive instinct has been identified and no support has been found for catharsis. The instinct theory cannot claim that physical education and sport programs provide a socially acceptable means of challenging natural aggressive urges.

The Frustration Aggression Theory sometimes called the drive theory states that violence is the direct result of a frustration that occurs because of goal blockage or failure (Dollard, Dood, Miller, Mowrer, & Seans 1939). The hypothesis at first made instinctive sense to psychologists because most aggressive acts are committed when people are frustrated. For example when a football player feels that an opponent has held him, he becomes frustrated and therefore hits the defender. However, this view hardly holds today because of its insistence that frustration must always

Cause aggression. Common experience shows that people often cope with their frustration or express it in non-aggressive fashion.

Social Learning Theory

According to Ne Laughlin (1971) social learning is a behavior learned interpersonal situation and linked to the

needs that they require for their satisfaction of the mediation of the people. This theory explains aggression as a behavior learned through observing other model behaviors for reimbursement to exhibit similar actions. Psychologist Albert Bandura (1973) found that children who watch adult models commit violent acts (beat up taboo dolls) repeated those act more than children unexposed to such aggressive models.

These effects were pronounced when children were reinforced for coping such actions of adult models.

Sport psychologists and other groups of sociologists referenced ice hockey and basketball as those encounters that required pervasiveness of illegal actions like fighting in such sports (Smith 1998) found that young players of the game model the violence prevalent in the professional games. In fact in hockey and basketball violence is valued such that players learned that being violent is a way to gain personal recognition. Today most coaches, parents and fans in some major sports accept that reinforce by cheering

Players for such aggressive behavior on the field of play (Smith 1988). Young players of Association football watch their heroes on the television screen, their model's aggressive behavior and receive reinforcement for exhibiting such similar behavior.

Revised Frustration

Aggression theory combines some elements of the frustration aggression and the social learning theory. This idea holds that though frustration does not always lead to violence, it increases the likelihood of aggression by increasing arousal and anger (Leonard Berkowitz, 1965, 1969) increased arousal and anger result in aggression when socially learned cues signal the appropriateness of aggression in a particular situation. If the socially learned cued signal that aggression is inappropriate, violence will not occur.

Violence is not new to physical activities and sports (during 1999, Guhmann, 1998) sport history has shown that the so-called blood sports were popular among the Ancient Greeks and it also was common among the Roman Empire. Death clouded the rituals of the games of Mayans and Aztecs. Tournaments during the medieval Ages and early modern Europe were organized as training grounds for war and warlike consequences.

Folk games were loosely governed rules and they produced injuries and death at alarming proportions. Bearbaiting, cock fighting, dog fighting and other sport activities during these periods involved the treatment of animals that most people would regard as the brutal and violent.

Research by figurational sociologists indicates that as part of an overall civilizing process of Europe and North America sports were developed as mere rule governed activities. As sports became formally organized official rules prohibit certain forms of violence that have been common in many folk games. Bloodshed decreased and there was emphasis on self-control to restrict physical contact and the expression of aggressive impulses often inspired by the emotional heat of competition (Dunning 1999). As figurational theorists have studied these changes, they have noticed that the rate of sports

violence do not decrease over time. Over all behavior and emotional expression in some societies become more regulated and controlled, many players and spectators are likely to experience more violence and aggression in sports as pleasurable and exciting. In addition, the process of globalization, commercialization and professionalism have given rise to new versions of instrumental and dramatic violence in many

Sports forms. Today as expressive violence has decreased, goal oriented violence has increased. Dunning (1999) notes that violence remains a crucial social issue in modern sports because sports activities are designed to create tension rather than relieve or discharge it, and sports continue to

Serve in patriarchal societies, as an arena in which aggression is used to reproduce an ideology of male dominance and privilege.

This study examined how explanation of the above theories is tied up with the causes and effects of sport violence in selected senior secondary schools in Bo city, southern Province, Sierra Leone.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study is initiated to;

1. Assess Principals/vice principals/PHE teachers/other teachers report on the frequency of accompanying their school teams for sport competition.
2. Examine Staff reports on the causes of violence in sports among school pupils.
3. Assess the rules and regulations of sporting activities.
4. Evaluate pupil's reports on methods used by school authorities to communicate rules and regulations of sports.
5. Examine staff reports on methods used to communicate sports rules and regulations.
6. Make necessary recommendations.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This was a descriptive study aimed at investigating the causes and effects of sport violence in selected senior secondary schools in Bo city, Southern Sierra Leone. Descriptive statistics, tables, charts and simple percentages were used to analyze the research findings so as to identify the nature/types, causes and effects of sport violence; the strategies put in place by school authorities and other sporting bodies to reduce or prevent sports violence; and identify suggestions from participants as to how sport violence can be reduced or prevented in the study area. Also, whether boys Suffered or perpetrated more crimes than girls, and the effects it has on perpetrators and victims.

Tables were used to describe the data collected from the two sets of questionnaires based on the research objectives. Statistical presentations were used to compare the differences observed in the schools.

The research findings were analyzed based on primary data related to the objectives of the study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table: Principal/Vice Principal Response on the Qualification of the Teachers/Coaches and Available Sport Facilities/Equipment.

School	No. of teachers per school	No. of PHE Teachers	Percentage of PHE Teachers	Qualification of PHE Teachers	Sport Facilities/ Equipment
Bo School	90	01	01%	HTC B. Ed	Volleyball Football Basketball Tennis Athletics track
Bo Commercial	98	02	02%	HTC. B. Ed	Volleyball Football Athletics field
CKC	68	02	2.9%	HTC	Volleyball Football Athletics field
QRS	30	02	6.6%	HTC	Athletics Field, Volleyball
UCC	51	03	5.9%	HTC B. Ed	Volleyball, football, athletics field

The above data revealed that these overcrowded schools have few PHE teachers with the UCC having 3 (5.9%) of a total 51 teachers, Bo Commercial, CKC, and QRS 2 PHE teachers each with Bo School on 1 (1%). It is obvious that during sports competitions, it is these few PHE teachers that accompany their athletics.

It is also likely that these few teachers and unqualified and unqualified coaches train student athletes for competitions.

Though all the PHE teachers posse the requisite qualification to handle

Courses as well as conduct school team yet their number is insignificant to the crowd when violence erupt.

The respondents of Appendix A recorded the following: following: Football field, volleyball court as the only facilities these schools have in common, except for Bo School with a complex for tennis, basketball and volleyball.

All the 5 schools (100) reported that they borrowed athletics equipment for their track and field athletics competitions. They also reported having few volleyballs, footballs which they use for training purposes as well as for competitions.

Comparing the large number of students in each of the schools, it can be concluded that students athletes have very

little time for training because of inadequate and low quality supply of sport equipment and facilities. Thus presenting unprepared for major competitions and with their expectation to win at all cost, might have led to sport violence especially during inter-soccer and volley competitions reporting the highest rate of sport violence among senior secondary school in the country.

Respondents of Appendix A were asked as to whether they have ever accompanied their school teams for any sport and competition. All (100%) respondents reported yes; whether they have done once, seldom, always.

Also, 10 (60%) of the schools reported to have accompanied their school teams seldom. 30% reported accompanying their school team always and 10% during so once.

Principals/Vice Principals/PHE Teachers/Other Teachers Report on the Frequency of Accompanying their School Teams for Sport Competition.

Schools	Frequency of Times		
Bo School	✓	-	-
Bo Commercial	-	✓	-
CKC	-	✓	✓
QRS	-	-	✓
UCC	-	✓	-
TOTAL	1	3	1
Percentage	20%	60%	20%

The above report indicate that the school authorities are often absent from school sport ground, which subsequently warranted student-athletes to be involved in perpetrating violence. Most students fear and respect only their school teachers. In cases where the school authorities are present on sports grounds, the number of staff is often insignificant compared to the

Students' population size, and in which case may not be able to exercise full control over them.

Appendix A further requested respondents to make a list of causes of sport violence. Of the causes listed were:

- Lack of knowledge of the rules and regulations of the sport on the side of the coaches, athletes and spectators
- coaches/spectators expectations
- lack of proper equipment and facilities
- improper training of participating teams/unprepared teams
- use of drugs
- poor officiating; and (partial decision) Motivation/rewards/celebration of victory

Staff Reports on the Causes of Violence in Sports among Selected Schools.

Schools	Causes					
	Ignorance of the laws	Coach/Spectator Expectation	Drugs	Improper Training	Poor officiating	Motivation/Reward
Bo school	2	1	1	-	1	-
Bo Commercial	2	1	1	-	-	1
CKC	1	2	-	1	1	-
QRS	2	-	2	-	-	1
UCC	2	2	-	-	1	-
TOTAL	9	6	4	1	3	2
Percentage	36%	24%	16%	4%	12%	8%

The responses in the table above seems to tally with the opinion of the researchers who suggested among others that ignorance of the laws of the game, drugs, improper training, poor officiating, poor equipment, inadequate accommodation for spectators and motivation/rewards/celebration of victory as sources of acts of violence-safa net 2001; Terry and Jackson 1985, Leonard 1988.

Respondents of Appendix A were also asked to select the competition in which violence was most prevalent among others. In the secondary school volleyball and soccer completion were 100% selected. This makes it clear that there were certain characteristics that make one school violent to another.

Whether there was a committee in each of the schools responsible to educate students and student-athletes about sports, all respondents of Appendix A answered yes. On the methods of how these rules were communicated, 14 (56%) members of the staff used the field to talk to the students, 8 (32%) did so during school devotion.

Staff Reports on Methods Used to Communicate Sports Rules and Regulation

Schools	Methods			
	Devotion	PHE Lessons	Fields	Others
Bo school	-	1	4	-
Bo Commercial	-	2	3	-
CKC	1	2	2	-
QRS	-	1	4	-
UCC	-	1	4	-
PERCENTAGE	12%	32%	56%	-

The above report indicate the most popular means for teaching students about the rules and regulations of sports, which is very common cause of sport violence, is done in the field during competitions. This means that students may not very knowledgeable of the rules of the sports and may intentionally flout these rules.

From the above, PHE lessons as a means of used to communicate the rules of sports to student ranked second. This might as well mean that it was the PHE teachers who named their lessons as means through which they communicate the rules of sport to students and student-athletes. The disadvantage of this method is that not every student in senior secondary school classes offers PHE lessons. Some schools do not offer it at all in their secondary school class. 3 out of 25 (12%) of the respondents named the devotion as or the place where rules and regulations of sports are communicated. It is likely that school principals who for most time use the devotion as a place for reaching out to students named this method. 14 (56%) of the respondents however suggested using the tree methods outlined in the questionnaire. This might be as a result of their increased awareness of the rate of sports violence and may want to control it.

Respondents of Appendix A were asked about the existence of sport disciplinary committee in their schools. A total of 18 (72%) of them said no, whilst 7 (28%) answered yes.

Staffs Reports on the Existence of a Disciplinary Committee in their Schools

Schools	Existence of Disciplinary Committee	
	Yes	No
Bo school	2	3
Bo Commercial	1	4
CKC	2	3
QRS	2	3
UCC	-	5
Total	7	18
Percentage	28%	72%

When asked to name two persons/groups in the setting up of measures or policies aimed at discouraging perpetrators of sport violence from their acts, PHE teachers were persons named by the respondents followed by some members of staffs of the school disciplinary committees. This to some extent can cause violence in sports as there can be corporate body in the school charged with the responsibilities of ensuring that students do not break the rules and regulations in sports. This committee should be given the mandate to use regulations meant to discourage students from being violent. Such a committee was never named by any of the respondents from schools.

On the question on whether the respondents have ever seen a student or student-athlete take drug or alcohol around sports area, all 25 (100%) said yes. Cannabis Sativa (Jamba) cigarette and beer were named as the most common drugs being used by athletes and supporters. This indicates that one of the causes of violence in school sports in the selected area is the use of drugs and alcohol as were reported by the respondents.

Drugs and alcohol have very negative effects on athletes and spectators' judgment as they have to do with the mind. Most of the alcohol is bottled,

For example, star beer. A supporter who perceives an official as being unfair to his or her school team may use the empty pint to harm the official. He/she may attack a student/supporter of the opponent school since his or her perception is impaired. This can also occur to active participants (Student-athletes) which may sometimes lead to athletes attacking the opponent or the supporter. Attacks on athletes were however not reported as a problem as it is very cases that they are attacked.

Students and student-athletes were provided with questionnaire different from the one for school authorities. On this questionnaire, respondents were as whether they have witnessed a competition in which an official (referee) made an unfair judgment leading to the loss of their school team

Students and Students-Athletes Reports on their Perception about Unfair Judgment of Officials

Schools	Officials Judgment	
	Unfair	Fair
Bo school	38	12
Bo Commercial	50	-
CKC	46	04
QRS	35	15
UCC	45	05
Total	214	36
Percentage	85.6%	14.4%
Sector	308.2 ⁰	52.8 ⁰

From the above table, 214 (85.6%) respondents indicated they have suffered unfair judgment from officials/referees. 36 (14.4%) responded not to have been judged unfairly by match officials. The huge difference in students' perception of officials being unfair might be a cause of violence in sports as students can easily start attacking opponents and officials whenever unfair judgments are made. It might as well be that some of these judgments were true whilst others were not as shown by the 36 (14.4) respondents that never perceive their officials as being unfair in their judgments.

Students reports about on methods used by school authorities to communicate rules and regulations of sports

Schools	Methods			
	Devotions	PHE Lessons	During Practices	None
Bo school	05	40	05	-
Bo Commercial	05	15	15	15
CKC	10	15	15	10
QRS	05	25	15	05
UCC	05	25	15	05
TOTAL	30	120	65	35
PERCENTAGE	12%	48%	26%	14%

There were however some differences between the reports given by respondents of Appendix A and those of Appendix B on the methods through which the rules and regulations of games of were communicated. 14 (56%) of the respondents of Appendix A name the field as opposed to 65 (26%) of the respondents of Appendix B who reported during practice in the field as a place where they were taught the laws of the games. Also

HE lessons were mostly reported by respondents of Appendix B- 120 (48%) as the most popular means used to teach the students the laws of the games opposed to 8 (32%) reported by respondents of Appendix A. Slight difference is seen in the use of the school devotions as a place

Where rules were communicated to students- 3 (12%) of the respondents of Appendix A as to 30 (125) of the respondents of Appendix B.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Violence in sport especially as it relates to selected senior secondary competitions is an important and highly publicized topic. Violence in the form of excessive physical force has led to greater loss of athletes and supporters, spectators, fans, cheers, the destruction of the equipment, demolition of infrastructure additionally, tarnishing the image of this noble institution organized sports. Using this as a premise, the research was conducted to investigate into the causes and effects of sports violence Among selected secondary schools in Bo City; strategies put in place to minimize violence in sports; identity suggestions from players and key stakeholders as to how violence in school sports can be prevented; control and to institute policy, recommendations based on research findings or outcomes.

Sports violence was defined as any form of behavior directed towards the goal of harming or injuring another person, who is motivated to avoid such

Treatment. Such behavior occurs outside the rules of sports and is unrelated to the competitive objectives of the intended sports.

The causes and effect of sports Violence

According to the findings of the research, key issues such as lack of knowledge about the rules of various sports was identified as a cause of violence in school sports as respondents saw referees and other members of the official crew as inconsistent/unfair in their judgment Coaches/spectators/supporters/expectations/rewards have great toll on the occurrence of violence in sports as the athletes desire to achieve rewards and coaches/spectators/supporters wanting their athletes to win at all cost in pursuance of which athletes might do anything even at the expense of the rules of the various sports.

Teachers' qualification and experience often serve a lot in meeting high standards of discipline and in preventing violence in sports. So too to the availability of sports facilities and equipment used in sports. These contribute immensely in the training of athletes since the unpreparedness for competition can sometimes lead to violence especially where champions may want to maintain their record but may not have prepared well. With this in mind, school administrators (principals/vice principals were asked to state the number of PHE teachers/team coaches in their

Schools and their qualifications including available equipment/facilities. Their responses were recorded as shown in the table below:

The findings of this research indicate that students and student athletes had not got the requisite training before the competitions (lack of skills, social and psychological training) which are crucial for continues participation in sports. Ill-prepared teams resort to violent play especially when their endurance level runs out while they are losing.

The abuse of drugs and excess alcohol consumption on sport grounds were seen as problem that causes violence in sports. Students, student athletes, their supporters misuse drugs and take alcohol to influence and Enhance their performance on field of play. Although supporters and spectators take drugs and alcohol with the pretext of refreshing and relaxing themselves, excessive use may impair their judgments and thus exhibit violent behavior out of sport rules.

In the absence of school administrator/school authorities, it is obvious that all motivated students may exhibit unsportsmanlike behavior during and after competitions. This research proves that the absence of school authorities on the sport grounds as students and student athletes may use

The glaring absence of teachers as a field day behavior on and out of the field.

School authorities indicated the method through which committers of violence in sport were reprimanded.

But the findings of the study made it clear that the modalities or methods were inappropriate to curb or control violence in school sport. For the non-existence of committees in the respective schools to properly handle perpetrators of sport violence. Instead the respective authorities relied on existing disciplinary committees that were reported to be

hardly prevented on sport grounds. The effective ways of communicating rules and regulations was extremely crucial in the prevention of sport violence. From the research findings of the study it was evident that the inadequate methods of communicating sport rules to students such as bringing them during devotion during PHE lessons and during practice sessions, instead of incorporating and engaging student athletes into the policy formation process of drawing up laws against violence committers during competitions.

The perpetrators of sport violence, sport officials/referees spectators and even facilities and equipment have been all the means of sport violence. Athletes and coaches are stressful and find it difficult to sport by either being reprimanded by referees/umpires as a result of injury in their attempt to win their sports at all cost or being physically or verbally attacked. Supporters all suffer from sport violence because they usually faced attack from opponents especially when they are on they are on the winning end of the competitions.

Most times sport equipment and related facilities are destroyed when violent behavior over run sport activities, especially when supporters resort to the use of weapons such as broken bottles sticks and other missiles for the purpose of inflicting harm on opponents in and outside sport facilities.

Opinion and recommendations of various categories of respondents included the following

a) Respondents of Appendix A suggested that the issue of sport violence among secondary schools is high.

-Students and student athletes should be taught the philosophy of non-violence, respect for self and opponents and responsibility.

- Students (present and past) should be concretized about the fact that winning at all cost is not is not everything that matters in sport competitions.

- Physical health education teachers and other active lovers of sports should always accompany school teams during sport competitions.

- Law enforcing agents especially police officers should be invited and made to maintain law and order in and around sport area.

- Students and athletes should be included in law/rules committees and should also be involved in the implementation of such rules and regulations of violence free competitions.

-Schools authorities especially principals/senior teachers should ensure that effective and proper implementation of disciplinary actions meant for the perpetrators of sport violence be upheld.

-Parents and guardians should also help in sensitization of their wards about desirable sportsmanlike behavior at all times.

b) Respondents of Appendix B suggested/indicated that sports violence and the use of drugs and alcohol are still the recipe of sport violence in and around sports grounds. Therefore the policy should ensure that the sale and use of these items (drugs and alcohol) be discouraged. Those who abuse drugs should be arrested prosecuted, named and shamed.

c) Parents/Guardians indicated that:

- Abuse of drugs and alcohol has greatly influenced the perpetuation of violence in sports and defaulting schools

should be banned from participating in much love competition or school leagues.

-Students are prone to initiate the behavioral trait of others, therefore inter secondary school sport should be removed from the school curriculum.

-Students who are noted for perpetrating violence be expelled from schools.

Conclusions

When violence occurs in connection with the enforcement of norms, the protection of people and property or deviant unconformity to widely accepted norms, it may be approved and even regarded as necessary for the preservation of order or reaffirmation of important social norms. Therefore, violence is often and not always accepted and defined as legitimate, as when it is used by soldiers, police or athletes in pursuit of victories representing their communities.

Psychologists have advanced four theories recording the causes of violence.

1. Instinct theory
2. Frustration - Aggression Theory
3. Social Learning Theory
4. Revised Frustration - Aggression Theory

Sports violence has tremendous negative effects on students, athletes, sport officials, spectators and equipment alike. It's not likely to contain all the causes of violence considering the magnitude of such problems.

Based on the results of the findings the researcher made the following conclusions:

- That is violence in sports among secondary schools in the study area is on the increase.
 - That the following indicators of sport violence
 - Lack of knowledge of the laws of sports/games by students/athletes, some sport officials, coaches and well as some teachers put in charge of games and sports.
 - Supporters/coaches expectations for positive results (winning at all cost)
 - Lack of effective punishment mechanisms against committers of sport violence
 - Lack of adequate and standardized equipment/facilities for the effective training of student-athletes.
 - Employment of non-specialists to act as coaches for athletes/participants in school sport competitions.
 - Lack of parents/guardians involvement and absence of sport programs
 - Inadequate school methods to communicate the rules and regulations of games and sports to students and student-athletes.
 - Presentation of unprepared teams due to insufficient training and competitions.
 - Unfair judgment by sports and officials in favor of certain schools
 - Insufficient accommodation for spectators during competitions
3. Concern authorities have not still done much in addressing the level of sports violence among senior secondary schools.

4. Lack of good leadership between school administrators and games teachers.
5. Celebration of victory especially by cheer leaders

Recommendations

It is not expected that violence in sports among senior secondary schools can be easily eliminated, nor it is expected that concerned authorities can adequately address all the causes of social problems. But this should not however stop them from adopting other appropriate methods of retaining violence in sports. Based on the conclusion drawn from this study, the following are recommended for PHE teachers/coaches, school

Administrators and sports officials to adopt with the hope of curbing sports violence.

PHE Teachers/Coaches/Team Trainers/Other Teachers

Teachers/coaches are responsible for the skills, tactics and ethics of their players. They should teach students-athletes about the laws, and regulations of games and sport.

- Encourage players to enjoy the sport
- Encourage ethical behavior, such as respect for all players, referees and other officials.
- When teaching/coaching, they should teach students athletes to balance their desire to win with the need to play the game and sport in the connect spirit.
- They should be aware of their needs and abilities and try to protect them from injury.
- Coaches/trainers should be trained on the current rules and regulations of the sport. They should in turn provide skills, emotional and psychological training before competitions.
- As sport develops an important role in the study area, sport specialists, officials MEY&S should provide information for athletes, teachers, lecturers and researchers and teaching institutions as they all share knowledge available to team players.
- Following their school teams to every competition and should be able to sport well behaved athletes and other students (present and past) to the admiration and notice of school administration.
- Teach students and athletes about harmful effects of violence in sports

School Administration

- As staff meetings, principals/vice principals and other teachers should make it a policy statement that all school functions with sport competitions inclusive.
- Make it a policy that students and athletes be encouraged to attend sport competitions in their respective school uniforms. Defaulters should face the wrath of the disciplinary committees.
- Awards for incentives in the form of scholarships, stationary, recognition of exemplary behavior through words of encouragement at devotion be introduced in schools.

- Students and student-athletes, parents/guardians should be involved in the formation of rules and regulations against perpetrators of sport violence.

Sport officials

- There is need for good coaching education programs for sport officials/referees who deal with the student-athletes during
- Sports completion. Such education will make them effective in the interpretation of the rules.
- Sport officials should be fair in their judgments and not seen to be biased on prejudiced other schools.
- Be conversant with the current rules of the games and sports and be ready to communicate these rules to the participants at all times.
- Conduct training sessions for students and student-athletes where they can be concretized about technical fouls that athletes commit out of ignorance and how such can be corrected.
- Be trained and pose professional qualifications such as HTC/National Diploma in Sports Coaching and Management from recognized institutions.
- Conduct in-service referring/coaching courses to prepare PHE teachers and other teachers to be equipped with life skills
- It is necessary for training of school teams to obey the philosophy of violence free sports.

REFERENCES

- [1] alvis, Claire (1994). Self –help Magazines.
- [2] Coakley, T. (1982). Sports of Society issues and controversies (2nd Edition). St Lions C. V. Mosby Company.
- [3] Dobeneotte, Valevie (1988). Spectator Violence at Sports Events. What keeps enthusiastic fans in Bonds? The Physical and Sports Medicine, 16 (4) 203-11. EJ 372800.
- [4] Jountains and Gee (1988). P.E to 16, Heinema London.
- [5] Hellstedth, John C. Kids, Parents and Sports: some Questions and Answers.
- [6] Honeybrowne J. Hill, and Moors, H. (1996). Advanced Physical Education and Sports. Stanley Thornes Publisher Ltd.
- [7] Joe Eshys, Vic Guest, Judith Lawrence, Collin Jackson and Dec Buinage, (1987). Fundamentals of health and Physical Education. Heinemann Educational publishers.
- [8] Lee, Martin J. (1985). From Rivary to Hostility Among sports Fans, Quest 37 (1) 38-49.
- [9] Leonard, Wilbert Marcollus (1988). A sociological Perspective of sport (3rd Edition) New York.
- [10] Roskosz, Francis M. (1988, late winter). The paradoxes of play. The physical Educator, 45 (10 5-13 EJ 371284.
- [11] Terry, Peter C. and Jackson John J. (1985). The Determinants and Control of Violence on Sports Quest, 37 (1) 27-37.
- [12] Wienberg Gould, Robert S. Wainberg, university of North Colorando, (1995). Foundations of sport and Exercise Psychology. Human Kinetics (chap 25, p467-473).
- [13] Wandzilak, Thomas (1985). Values Development through physical Activity Promoting sports Manlike behaviours. Perceptions and Moral Reasoning. Journal of teaching in P.E. 8 (1) 19-21. WEISER, Kathy and Love, Phylis (1988, Sept. Oct). Who owns your Team? Strategies 2(1) 5 - 8